

ELECTROLYTIC PREPARATION OF COPPER ARSENATE

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The preparation of copper arsenate has been carried out by electrolysing a neutral solution of sodium arsenite in a diaphragm cell between copper anode and iron cathode. The influence on its production of the following parameters were studied: Sodium arsenite concentration, C.D., duration of electrolysis, addition of cerous oxide and temperature. The current efficiency under optimum conditions has been observed to be 60%.

Copper arsenate has been prepared from time to time by various chemical methods (Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Theoretical and Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. IX, p. 157); the products are usually contaminated with several impurities due to the formation of a large number of intermediate products. The possibilities of the electrolytic process have, however, not been hitherto investigated in adequate details in the field of copper arsenate preparation. But a review of literature shows that a series of investigations on the electrolytic preparation of sodium arsenate (Lowenstein, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1929, 76, preprint, 3, 29; Essin, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1929, 35, 234), calcium arsenate (Lloyd and Kennedy, *Chem. Met. Eng.*, 1925, 32, 624) and lead arsenate (Ormout, *Chem. J. Ukraine*, 1926, 2, 10) have been carried out by the oxidation of sodium arsenite using suitable anodes. In the present investigation an attempt has therefore been made to synthesise copper arsenate by the electrolysis of aqueous sodium arsenite solution using copper anodes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experiments were carried out in a diaphragm cell; it consists of a glass jar and a porous pot of capacities 1.5 and 1.0 litres respectively. The cell was kept immersed in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature within $\pm 0.5^\circ$. The anode used was a thin rectangular sheet (8.0 $\times$ 5.0 cm.) of copper and cathode, a thick iron plate (8.0 $\times$ 5.0 $\times$ 0.5 cm.). The catholyte in all cases was 3.0 g. of sodium nitrate dissolved in 300 c.c. of water.

Since the electrolysis was carried out in absolute neutral medium, the product of electrolysis in all cases was usually a bluish green precipitate containing copper arsenite and arsenate. In all estimations 0.2 g. of the precipitate was dissolved in hot dilute sulphuric acid and titrated against a standard potassium permanganate solution and the amount of copper arsenite was calculated. A second sample of 0.2 g. of the product was dissolved in about 20 c.c. of the acid and the requisite amount of sodium hydroxide solution was added to precipitate completely copper as copper hydroxide. The precipitate was filtered, washed well and dried. Finally it was weighed as copper oxide after incineration and thus the total amount of copper was computed. The filtrate contained both sodium arsenite and arsenate which was boiled with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the arsenic was estimated gravimetrically by precipitating

completely as arsenious sulphide. Thus the total quantity of arsenic was obtained and the quantity corresponding to arsenate content was determined. Copper arsenite is soluble in ethyl alcohol, whereas arsenate is insoluble, and the separation of the product was therefore carried out by using this solvent. In each experiment 1.0 g. of the mixture was taken, shaken well with the alcohol and filtered through a Gooch crucible. The residue was dried and weighed. Thus the amount of copper arsenate was determined. Each estimation was carried out at least twice. The mean value was invariably in agreement with those observed analytically.

The optimum concentration (cf. curve C₁, Fig. 1) and time (cf. curve C₃, Fig. 1) have been arrived at empirically.

To investigate the further optimum conditions for the production of copper arsenate the influence of the following factors was studied :

- (a) Current density (curve C₂, Fig. 1).
- (b) Addition of cerous oxide (curve C₄, Fig. 1).
- (c) Temperature (curve C₅, Fig. 1).

The anolyte in the following experiments contained 3 g. of sodium nitrate dissolved in 500 c.c. of water together with 12.5 g. of sodium arsenite neutralised by acetic acid. The potential difference across the cell was maintained at 25 volts.

Experiments on the Effect of Current Density.—Electrolysis was continued for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour at 28°. Results are plotted in curve C₂, Fig. 1.

Experiments on the Effect of Cerous Oxide.—Electrolysis was continued for 2 hours at 28° and at C. D. of 2.5 amp./dm². Results are plotted in curve C₄, Fig. 1.

Experiments on the Effect of Temperature.—Cerous oxide (0.5 g.) was added to the experimental electrolyte and electrolysis continued for 2 hours at a C.D. of 2.5 amp./dm². Results are plotted in curve C₅, Fig. 1.

The p_H of the anolyte remains constant during the electrolysis, whereas that of the catholyte varies from 7.0 to 11.1 at the optimum condition.

DISCUSSION

Curves (Fig. 1) show the influence of various parameters in the production of copper arsenate. It is observed that the copper arsenite is formed preferentially to copper arsenate in absence of an oxygen carrier, since the solution potential of copper and the oxidation potential of sodium arsenite are very close to each other.

Results (cf. curve C₁, Fig. 1) show that the current efficiency is low (4.09%) at a concentration of 10 g. of sodium arsenite/litre probably due to the lack of depolariser, sodium arsenite which consequently leads to much evolution of oxygen. The current efficiency increases with increase of concentration and reaches its maximum (16.69%) at 25 g./litre. Above this approximate concentration it decreases steadily due to the excess of depolariser which helps the formation of copper arsenite and subsequently lessens the yield of arsenate.

Data shown in curve C₂, Fig. 1 tend to prove the fact that in electrolytic oxidations, the potential for oxygen evolution is reached at relatively low current densities. A high concentration of depolariser opposes concentration polarisation and keeps down the

anode potential, whilst a high current density has the opposite effect. With C.D. of 2.5 amp./dm². the current efficiency reaches a maximum (16.69%). At higher C.D.s

FIG. 1

the efficiency decreases due to much current being wasted in discharging oxygen and hydrogen at the anode and cathode. Below C.D. 2.5 amp./dm², the efficiency falls possibly due to the decrease in oxygen overvoltage and much current being wasted in discharging oxygen.

The effect of duration of electrolysis is generally of considerable importance in all oxidation processes. Oxygen overvoltage increases towards a maximum value and then, in some cases, shows a slight decrease on continued electrolysis. This is actually exhibited in the case of copper arsenate (cf. curve C₃, Fig. 1). At 30 minutes the yield is low (16.7%) and gradually increases with time due to rise in oxygen overvoltage and reaches a maximum at about 2.0 hours. With the further progress of electrolysis the efficiency decreases gradually.

Not only the material of the electrode but also additions to electrolyte, can act as catalysts in anodic oxidations. Some of these oxygen carriers viz., cerous oxide, cerous sulphate are very important. The salts can readily be oxidised anodically to ceric one, powerful oxidising agents, which react readily with so many reducing substances

converting them smoothly and quantitatively into single oxidation products. The compound thus obtained will be reoxidised, the result of the whole operation being the quantitative oxidation of the depolariser (Allnand and Ellingham, "The Principles of Applied Electrochemistry", 2nd Ed., p. 105). So the effect of cerous oxide on the production of copper arsenate was studied (cf. curve C₄, Fig. 1). It is evident that the current efficiency steadily increases with the increased addition of cerous oxide and reaches 47.19% with 0.5 g. of the oxide.

The influence of an increase of temperature on an anodic oxidation during the evolution of oxygen may act favourably by increasing the velocity of diffusion of the depolariser; it may also lower the oxygen overvoltage and consequently facilitate the oxidation of the depolariser. It would be thus better to carry on the work at a high or a low temperature in accordance with one or other of these two effects predominates. At a certain temperature the arsenate formation is favoured and consequently the current efficiency and the yield per K. W. H. increase and at others they diminish appreciably. Thus in the electrolytic preparation of copper arsenate the best results are obtained at 40° (cf. curve C₅, Fig. 1).

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